

Benzyl Fluoride.—An alcoholic solution of benzyl bromide (18g.) was refluxed with anhydrous thallous fluoride (30 g.) for 32 hours. The filtrate of the reaction product was freed from alcohol on the water-bath and the residue distilled, when a light yellow viscous distillate was obtained, b.p. 140°. It is lachrymatory and decomposes slowly evolving hydrofluoric acid (Found : F, 17.00. Calc. for C_7H_7F : F, 17.27 per cent).

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Variation of Cataphoretic Velocity of Colloidal Particles during Aggregation. Part II.

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In a recent paper (Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Bhabak, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 370) it has been shown that for a number of colloids and electrolytes

(i) the cataphoretic velocity increases with time with progressing aggregation of the colloidal particles at a constant concentration of the added electrolyte;

(ii) the increase in c. v. with time is often more marked, the higher the valency of the precipitating ions;

(iii) the c. v. of the supernatant suspension of a colloid after partial coagulation is less than that of the colloid before coagulation;

(iiii) the c. v. of the coagula of a sol (As_2S_3) is the same as that of the supernatant suspension of the colloid after coagulation.

These results are contradictory to the existing theories (Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Bhabak, *loc. cit.*), which lay the main stress on the thickness and the capacity of the double layer, on the radius of the particle and on the ionic strength of the medium and neglect the changes in the distribution of ions on aggregation which appear to be more important than the factors just mentioned. An explanation on this basis has been put forward by Mukherjee. Chaudhury and Ghosh (*Trans. National Inst. Sci. India*, 1936, 1, 47-82) and by Mukherjee,

Chaudhury and Bhabak (*loc. cit.*). Further information is desirable on several points. In the present paper these observations have been extended to a wider range of concentrations of electrolytes and several other colloids. Some of the previous experiments have been confirmed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the Colloids.

Arsenious Sulphide.—25 C.c. of a saturated solution of As_2O_3 in distilled water were diluted with an equal volume of water and then mixed up with 500 c.c. of water saturated with hydrogen sulphide. Hydrogen sulphide washed through water was then passed till there was no further change in colour. Hydrogen gas was then bubbled through the solution to free it from excess of H_2S .

Vanadium Pentoxide.—About 10 g. of ammonium vanadate was triturated in a mortar with a few drops of strong hydrochloric acid till the mass was converted into a deep red paste. This was washed with several changes of water till the mass began to peptise. It was then shaken up with a large volume of water resulting in a dark red stable sol (sp. condty., 5×10^{-4} mho.).

Selenium Hydrosol.— H_2SeO_3 was added in minute quantities to about 3 c.c. of $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the precipitated Se was peptised by shaking. The resultant dark red solution was diluted till no appreciable opalescence appeared (sp. condty., 7×10^{-4} mho.).

Uranyl Ferrocyanide.—Equal volumes of 0.1 N- $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, $3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were mixed together and the resulting precipitate washed by centrifuging with conductivity water till a stable sol was obtained. The larger particles were removed by centrifuging the sol (sp. condty., 5×10^{-3} mho.).

Copper Ferrocyanide.—It was prepared in the same way as uranyl ferrocyanide using (0.1N) solutions of CuSO_4 , $5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$. The larger particles were removed by centrifuging this sol (sp. condty., 3×10^{-4} mho.).

Hydrated Ferric Oxide.—To a litre of boiling conductivity water about 100 c. c. of an approximately 5% ferric chloride solution were added with stirring and the boiling continued for another 10-15 minutes. The sol was black in reflected light. It was then dialysed in a parchment bag for four days (sp. condty., 4×10^{-4} mho.).

The Parabolic Curve.

The cataphoretic velocities of particles at different depths of a cell when plotted against their respective depths should give a parabolic curve (Smoluchowski, Graetz, "Handbuch der Elektrizität u.d.

Curves 1 and 2 refer respectively to suspensions after coagulation with NaCl and BaCl₂.

Curves 1-3 refer respectively to pure sol, N/80-KCl and N/160-KCl.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to N/1000-KCl, pure sol, N/800- and N/1500-KCl.

Curve 1 refers to Se sol and curve 2 to hydrated Fe₂O₃ coagulated by K-oxalate.

Magnetismus", 1914, II, 2, p. 383). Observations were made with the pure sols excepting As_2S_3 and $Fe(OH)_3$, where in the pure sols, the particles were too small to be visible under the microscope and readings were taken after coagulation of this sol with solid $NaCl$ (Fig. 1) or $N/300-BaCl_2$ (Fig. 1). The ferric oxide sol was also coagulated by ($N/525$) potassium oxalate (Fig. 4). The V_2O_5 and uranyl ferrocyanide sols were also mixed with equal volumes of such concentrations of KCl as would not cause any appreciable coagulation and therefore the c.v. should not vary during the interval of the experiment (Figs. 2 and 3 respectively).

FIG. 5.
 As_2S_3 sol.

Curves 1-3 refer respectively to $N/25$, $N/20$ - and $N/16-HCl$.

FIG. 7.
 V_2O_5 sol.

Curves 1-3 refer respectively to $N/40$, $N/45$ - and $N/50-KCl$.

FIG. 6.
 As_2S_3 sol.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to $N/5$, $N/7$, $N/8$ - and $N/10-NaCl$ and curve 5 to $N/8-KCl$.

FIG. 8.
 V_2O_5 sol.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to $N/1500$, $N/1800$, $N/2000$ - and $N/2500-BaCl_2$.

From Figs. 1 to 8, it is found that with low concentrations of electrolytes such as would not produce any perceptible coagulation, the parabolic form of the curve required by Smoluchowski's theory is verified to an accuracy obtained by other authors (Abramsohn, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1929, **12**, 711; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, **35**, 331). The above results could be reproduced only when the cell is carefully cleansed. The c.v. values are found to be reproducible within $\pm 1\%$.

RESULTS.

In the following are given the references to the figures, illustrating the effect of different electrolytes on the c.v. of various colloids with time.

No.	Sol.	Electrolytes used	Figs. for reference
1	As ₂ S ₃	KCl; NaCl, HCl	5 and 6
2	V ₂ O ₅	KCl; BaCl ₂ ; AlCl ₃	7, 8 and 9
3	Se	Do	10, 11, 12.
4	Cu ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	Do	13, 14.
5	(UO ₂) ₂ Fe(CN) ₆	KCl, BaCl ₂	15
6	Fe(OH) ₃	KCl; BaCl ₂ ; K-oxalate, K-citrate	16
7	As ₂ S ₃	KCl	17

In Figs. 13 and 15, the effect on c. v. of both peptisation and coagulation is given together. Equal volumes (100 c.c. each) of the precipitants (0.1N) were mixed together (CuSO₄, 5H₂O + K₄Fe(CN)₆, 3H₂O) in case of Cu₂Fe(CN)₆ and UO₂(NO₃)₂, 6H₂O + K₄Fe(CN)₆, in case of (UO₂)₂Fe(CN)₆. The precipitate was washed by centrifuging, using 200 c. c. conductivity water each time till the precipitate peptised to give a stable sol. The c.v. was measured after each washing. After keeping for a few days, the c. v. was found to increase. A decrease was observed after centrifugalisation of the sol (*cf.* Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 431). The centrifuged sol was taken and the c.v. noted with time as usual after adding different electrolytes mentioned above.

FIG. 9.
V₂O₅ sol.

Curves 1-5 refer respectively to N/5000-, N/6000-, N/6500-, N/7000- and N/10000-AlCl₃.

FIG. 10.
Se sol.

Curves 1-5 refer respectively to N/2-, N/5-, N/8-, N/10-, and N/20-KCl.

FIG. 11.
Se sol.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to N/20-, N/50-, N/100-, and N/500-BaCl₂.

FIG. 12.
Se sol.

Curves 1 and 2 refer respectively to N/1000- and N/1200-AlCl₃.

An analysis of the results obtained shows that the c.v. of a colloid always increases with time in presence of coagulating concentrations of electrolytes (Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Bhabak, *loc. cit.*) and when the time of observation is prolonged, a decrease in the c. v.

is observed. Moreover, another characteristic, quite often observed with the colloids and electrolytes so far studied, is that for higher concentrations of an electrolyte, the percentage increase in the c. v. observed with time is always larger. At low concentrations of electrolytes, irregular variations in the c. v. have been observed. Thus with arsenious sulphide sol and 0.04N-HCl there is observed an abnormal increase in c. v. after 2 hours of the mixing of the colloid and the electrolyte, followed by a sharp decrease. In the presence of 0.12N-NaCl, the variations in the c. v. of a colloid are also irregular, (cf. Figs. 5 and 6).

Vanadium Pentoxide Sol.—Curve 2, Fig. 7 and curve 4, Fig. 8 are exceptions to the concentration effect, *i.e.*, the greater the concentration taken, the larger the percentage of increment in c. v. with time. The concentration effect is clearly evident with V_2O_5 hydrosol and $AlCl_3$ (Fig. 9). Comparing Figs. 7, 8 and 9, it would appear that there is a valency effect, *i.e.*, the higher the valency of the precipitating ion, the larger the percentage increase in c. v.

FIG. 13.

 $Cu_2 Fe(CN)_6$

No. of washing. Time (min.).
Curves 1-3 refer respectively to N/200-KCl, N/500- and N/1000 $BaCl_2$.

FIG. 14.

 $Cu_2 Fe(CN)_6$ sol.

1—N/60-KCl; 2—N/4000- $AlCl_3$;
3—N/5000- $AlCl_3$; 4—N/1000- $BaCl_2$;
5—N/50-KCl; 6—N/800- $BaCl_2$.

Selenium Sol.—(i) With KCl, curve 2, Fig. 10 is an exception to the concentration effect.

(ii) With $BaCl_2$ the concentration effect is pronounced (curve 1, Fig. 11). At lower concentrations there is at first a decrease

FIG. 16.
Fe(OH)₃ sol.

1— N/KCl ; 2— $N/2-KCl$; 3— $N/2-KCl$;
4— $N/800-K-citrate$; 5— $N-BaCl_2$; 6— $N/600$
K-oxalate; 7— $N/525-K-oxalate$; 8— $N/550-$
K-oxalate.

FIG. 17.
As₂S₃ sol.

$N/12-KCl$.

DISCUSSION.

It would appear from the curves that the rate of cataphoresis runs somewhat parallel to the rate of coagulation and that none of the theories of cataphoresis is sufficient to explain these results of diverse character, for the simple reason that in the theories of cataphoresis in presence of electrolytes, no account has so far been taken of the equilibrium between the process of aggregation and de-aggregation of the colloidal particles (*vide supra*).

The kinetics of the coagulation of a colloid by an electrolyte has been dealt with theoretically by Smoluchowski (*Kolloid Z.*, 1916, **18**, 190) and various attempts to verify it experimentally have been made by different investigators, notably by Westgren and Reitsstötter (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1918, **92**, 750), Mukherjee and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **117**, 1564; 1924, **125**, 785), Desai and co-workers (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, **24**, 181; *Kolloid Chem. Beih.*, 1928, **26**, 357; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, **26**, 138) and recently by Joshi and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 11, 337; 1932, **9**, 157; 1933, **10**, 329; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, *Ray Comm. Vol.*, 1931, p. 41).

As a result of these investigations it has been found that

(i) With low concentrations of electrolytes, initially Smoluchowski's equation holds good but afterwards there are marked deviations. These are not the only results contrary to the expectations from the theory of Smoluchowski, but great irregularities and discontinuities in the coagulation process have been reported (Joshi and co-workers, *loc. cit.*).

(ii) At high concentrations of electrolytes, Smoluchowski's equation has been generally found to hold good.

As has been pointed out under the section "Results" that very often at the high concentrations of electrolytes, the percentage increase in c. v. with time is larger as the concentration of the electrolyte increases and that higher the valency of the precipitating ions, the greater is the percentage increment. This is to be expected from the theory of Smoluchowski on the basis of the hypothesis suggested by us (*loc. cit.*) that the increase in c. v. is the outcome of the aggregation of the particles. The higher the stage of aggregation or perhaps the more closely and intensely the primary particles are held in the aggregate, the greater is the percentage increase in the c. v. It is of interest to note that a possible explanation of the failure of Smoluchowski's theory at concentrations other than those producing rapid coagulation consists in the inhibiting effect of an increase in the c. v., i.e., potential of the double layer (*cf.* Mukherjee and Majumdar, *loc. cit.*). A correlation in the observed changes in c. v. with the kinetics of the coagulation is very much desirable and it is hoped to deal with this aspect in a future communication.

The rate of coagulation by an electrolyte or the coagulating power of an electrolyte is known to depend on the quality of the sol including its contents of free electrolytes, specially of ions which are constituents of the colloidal substance. Dhar and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 31) report that the purer the sol, the less is the valency effect. In case of uranium and copper ferrocyanide hydrosols which perhaps contain only small amounts of free electrolytes as would appear from their method of preparation and the specific conductivity of the order of 10^{-5} mho., the valency effect as observed by us in other cases disappears.

In the case of other sols the valency effect is quite marked though concentration effect is not so regularly pronounced. But the specific conductivities of other sols where the valency effect is quite marked are not materially different from that of the copper and uranium ferrocyanide sol, though it is somewhat larger. Further, with these sols the

concentration effect is not so well pronounced. Potassium chloride quite often forms an exception to the concentration effect and hydrogen chloride shows a very great increase in the c. v. with time. The curves for arsenious sulphide (*cf.* Figs. 5 and 6) show greater irregularity than similar curves for other sols. This is presumably due to complex nature of As_2S_3 sol and to the presence of polythionic acids and colloidal sulphur (Mukherjee and Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **2**, 296).

It would thus appear that the cataphoretic velocity of a colloid depends more on the condition of aggregation of the colloids than on the nature and concentration of the electrolytes taken, these latter two affecting the c. v. of a colloid in so far as they do it by producing a certain stage of aggregation in the system. Thus it also follows as a corollary that the postulate of the coagulation of a colloid taking place at a critical potential even in presence of multivalent precipitating ions is quite untenable in view of the facts presented in this and other papers (*cf.* Mukherjee Chaudhury and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*).

SUMMARY.

The observations so far made may be summarised as follows.—

1. In presence of coagulating concentrations of electrolytes
 - (a) The higher the valency of the precipitating ion, the greater is the percentage increase in c. v. observed with time.
 - (b) The higher the concentration of the electrolyte taken, the greater is the percentage increase in c. v. observed with time.
 - (c) In some sols where the purity of the sol is comparatively greater, effect (a) disappears—just as the valency effect on the coagulating powers of electrolytes disappears in the case of extremely pure sols.
2. In the region of slow coagulation, *i.e.*, with low concentrations of electrolytes there are discontinuities of an irregular nature observed in the variation of c. v. with time, similar to those observed in the rate of coagulation of colloids with low concentrations of electrolytes.
3. Moreover, the variation of c. v. with time in presence of an electrolyte appears to depend on (i) the nature of the sol; (ii) the nature of the electrolyte added and (iii) the electrolytic content of the sol—conditions on which also depends the rate of coagulation of different colloids in presence of various electrolytes.